

Efficient Nonparametric Estimation in Randomized Block Designs with Right-Censored Data

Nabanita Kakati¹, Bipin Gogoi²

¹Teaching Assistant, Dept. of Statistics, Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh, India

²Rtd. Professor, Department of Statistics, Dibrugarh University, Assam, India

Abstract

This study presents a nonparametric approach to analyzing randomized block designs with randomly right-censored data. In this article, we study about the statistics viz. Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya, Woolson-Lachenbruch, Mack and Skillings, and F-test procedures based on Gehan and Log-rank score in randomized block design with more than one observation per cell. We have used uniform censoring of observations for the study. Observations were taken from exponential distributions and Weibull distributions for the study to test the hypothesis. We noticed performance of Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya test is comparatively lower than Woolson-Lachenbruch type Log-rank test in uniform censoring distributions.

Keywords: Randomized block design, randomly right-censoring, uniform censoring, exponential distribution, and Weibull distribution.

1. Introduction

Randomized block designs are frequently employed to lower variability and boost the accuracy of statistical comparisons between various treatment groups. This study analyzed nonparametric tests that work with the randomized block design structure to allow for right-censored observations. In experimental design, blocking is designed to account for the variation between blocks to improve the accuracy of the main effects of the treatments. The main effects in an experimental setting might not always translate to other settings, particularly when interactions or intricate relationships are present. One of the primary objectives of most statistical data collection is to identify the factors contributing to the variation in the variable under study. In the literature of nonparametric statistics, Friedman's test for the problems of

main effects in two-way experimental design is commonly applied, though it has a relatively low asymptotic efficiency. This test used block ranks for statistical analysis and was used in the case where each cell had one observation [1]. Lehman focused on estimating and testing arbitrary contrasts within the factors of interest [2]. Bhapkar and Gore suggested nonparametric tests for the permutation invariance hypothesis in hierarchical data [3]. Gore extended Friedman's test for multiple observations per cell [4].

Several distribution-free tests are available in randomized block designs. However, censoring in randomized block design is not widely utilized because censoring can affect the estimation of treatment effect due to incomplete data. Gehan (1965) introduced an extension of the distribution free two samples Wilcoxon's test to samples with arbitrarily right censoring [5]. Again, Breslow generalized Gehan's test for k-populations of right-censored observations. This statistic has asymptotic chi-squared distributions under their null hypothesis for random censoring variables [6]. Patel (1975) proposed an extended Friedman test in randomized block design for observations when subject to arbitrary right censorship [7]. Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya (2014) generalized the Gore test for the observations when subject to arbitrary right censorship in the case of randomized block design [8].

In this paper, we studied the performance of Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya's test for uniform and exponential censoring datasets in randomized block design. This test also compares with the Woolson-Lachenbruch type method, Friedman type methods, and F-test utilizing Gehan score and log-rank procedures.

Test Procedures

The linear model of a two-way layout is considered as

$$X_{ijl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \varepsilon_{ijl} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where μ is the mean effect, α_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, r$) effect of the i^{th} treatment effect, β_j ($j=1, 2, \dots, c$) effect of j^{th} block and ε_{ijl} ($l = 1, 2, \dots, n_{ij}, n_{ij} \geq 1$) is the random error component. Let (X_{ijl}, δ_{ijl}) denote l^{th} observations on i^{th} treatments in the j^{th} block and

$$Y_{ijl} = \min(X_{ijl}, Z_{ijl}) \text{ and } \delta_{ijl} = 1 \text{ if } Y_{ijl} = X_{ijl}$$

$$= 0 \quad \text{Otherwise}$$

Where the uncensored continuous random variables X_{ijl} 's are distributed with the distribution function $F_{ij}(x)$. Here, Z_{ijl} , $i=1, 2, \dots, r, j=1, 2, \dots, c$ and $l=1, 2, \dots, n_{ij}$ the censoring variables are distributed independently on Y_{ijl} 's. Also $\sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_i = \sum_{j=1}^c \beta_j = 0$, without loss of generality.

The null hypothesis of the study is

$$H_0 = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \dots = \alpha_r ; \text{ that means treatment effects are equal.}$$

On the other hand, at least one treatment effect is not equal to the alternative hypothesis.

1.1 Test Statistic

Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya (2014) suggested a generalized version of the Gore test for censoring with $i \neq i'$ score function is

$$\varphi_{ii'jl'l'}(Y_{ijl}, \delta_{ijl}; Y_{i'jl'}, \delta_{i'jl'}) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } Y_{ijl} < Y_{i'jl'} \text{ and } \delta_{ijl} = 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } Y_{i'jl'} < Y_{ijl} \text{ and } \delta_{i'jl'} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \dots (3)$$

And $T_i = \sum_{i' \neq i} \sum_{j=1}^b U_{ii'j}$, $i=1, 2, \dots, t, j=1, 2, \dots, b$.

Where, $U_{ii'j} = \frac{1}{n_{ij}n_{i'j}} \sum_{l=1}^{n_{ij}} \sum_{l'}^{n_{i'j}} \varphi_{ii'jl'l'}(Y_{ijl}, \delta_{ijl}; Y_{i'jl'}, \delta_{i'jl'})$

Under the null hypothesis

$$E(U_{ii'j}) = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$V(U_{ii'j}) = \frac{n_{ij} + n_{i'j}}{n_{ij}n_{i'j}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - F_j^0(x))^2 (1 - I_j(x))^2 dF_j^0(x)$$

$$+ \frac{2}{n_{ij}n_{i'j}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - F_j^0(x)) F_j^0(x) d\tilde{F}_j^0(x)$$

$$\text{Cov}(U_{ii'j}, U_{ii''j}) = \frac{1}{n_{ij}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - F_j^0(x))^2 (1 - I_j(x))^2 dF_j^0(x)$$

For an equal number of observations (when $n_{ij} = n$) the test statistic is

$$S_1^* = \frac{N}{r^3 c \hat{h}(F)} \sum_{i=1}^t T_i^2 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Where $\hat{h}(F) = \frac{1}{n^3 r^3} \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{i'=1}^t \sum_{l'=1}^n \delta_{i'jl'} [\sum_{i'=1}^t \sum_{l'=1}^n \varepsilon(Y_{ijl} - Y_{i'jl'})]^2$

Here $\varepsilon(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases}$

Under the null hypothesis, S_1^* would be rejected if S_1^* exceeds the $\alpha\%$ critical points.

When N is sufficiently large S_1^* is approximately distributed as a chi-square with (t - 1) df.

1.2 Woolson-Lachenbruch Type Statistic

In the analysis of censored data, especially in survival analysis, Gehan and log-rank scores are often utilized. These scores deal with censored observations when a variable's precise value is not recorded but is only known to surpass or fall short of an initial threshold. Groggel et al. (1987) introduced a distribution-free test statistic in the Woolson-Lachenbruch type method for multiple observations in cells using these tests for censored data. For the ij^{th} ($i=1, 2, \dots, t, j=1, 2, \dots, b$ and $l=1, 2, \dots, n$) observation U_{ijl} , the Gehan score is the number of observations in the j^{th} block, known to be less than Y_{ijl} minus the number of observations known to exceed Y_{ijl} defined as

$$U_{ijl} = \sum_{a=1}^t \sum_{b=1}^n [I(Y_{ijl} > Y_{ajb}) \delta_{ajb} - I(Y_{ijl} < Y_{ajb}) \delta_{ijl}] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Where $I(A) = 1$, if A occurs

= 0, otherwise

After replacing the rank R_{ijl} in Y_{ijl} the log rank can be written as

$$L_{ijl} = \sum_{a=1}^t \sum_{b=1}^n \frac{I(Y_{ijl} \geq Y_{ajb}) \delta_{ajb}}{(tn+1 - R_{ajb})} - \delta_{ijl} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Assuming S_{ijl} is the score (Gehan or log-rank in eq (5) or (6)) for the ijl^{th} observation. Let

$$W_i = \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^n S_{ijl} \text{ and } W' = (W_1, W_2 \dots W_t) \dots\dots (7)$$

Under H_0 , $E(W_i) = 0$, $V(W_i) = \frac{n(t-1)}{t(nt-1)}A$ and $Cov(W_i, W_a) = \frac{-n}{t(nt-1)}A$

Where, $A = \sum_{i=1}^t \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^n S_{ijl}^2$. When the null hypothesis is true, the vector

$$H = \left[\frac{(nt-1)}{nA} \right]^{1/2}$$

is true with mean zero, and the rank of the idempotent covariance matrix is $(t - 1)$. Also, for $n \rightarrow \infty$ (when b is fixed), H follows an asymptotically normal distribution (Breslow, 1970). Again, for fixed ‘ n ’, as $b \rightarrow \infty$ H follows asymptotically normal. Using these results, the conditional distribution of $H'H$ is limiting ($n \rightarrow \infty, b \rightarrow \infty$) as chi-square with $(t-1)$ df. Thus, an approximate test for H_0 can be conducted by rejecting H_0 if

$$T = \frac{(nt-1)}{nA} \sum_{i=1}^t W_i^2 \dots\dots (9)$$

exceeds the upper 100% limits for chi-square distributions. T is referred to as TG for the Gehan score and TL for log-rank scores.

1.3 Friedman-Type Statistic

One of the benefits of transforming observations into scores S_{ijl} is that it allows for logical comparisons based on the order values. Therefore, Groggel, D. J., Schaefer, R. L., and Skillings, J. H. (1987) extended the Mack and Skillings’ Friedman type test for the two-way layout using ranks on the score. The test statistic is

$$FT = \frac{12b}{N(N+b)} \sum_{i=1}^t \left[\sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^n r_{ijl} - \frac{N+b}{2} \right]^2 \dots\dots (10)$$

Where, r_{ijl} be the rank of S_{ijl} and $N = tbn$. After applying the Gehan score (eq. 5) and Log-rank (eq. 6) on FT, the test is denoted as FTU and FTL, respectively. The statistic FT has

an asymptotic chi-square distribution as $b \rightarrow \infty$, and $n \rightarrow \infty$ with $t-1$ degrees freedom. One important drawback of the test FT is that a high percentage of censored observations within a block can result in several ties in the S_{ijl} . With the help of mid-rank, tie-breaking can be done.

1.4 F-Test

The F-test for testing the hypothesis of cell sizes ($n_{ij} = n$) in the randomized block design is

$$F = \frac{\left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^t \frac{x_{i..}^2}{bn} \right) - \left(\frac{x_{...}^2}{tbn} \right) \right] / (t-1)}{\left[\sum_i \sum_j \sum_l x_{ijl}^2 - \left(\sum_i \frac{x_{i..}^2}{tn} \right) - \left(\sum_j \frac{x_{.j.}^2}{tn} \right) + \left(\frac{x_{...}^2}{tbn} \right) \right] / (tbn - t - b + 1)} \quad \dots (5)$$

Where, $x_{i..} = \sum_j \sum_l x_{ijl}$, $x_{.j.} = \sum_i \sum_l x_{ijl}$, $x_{...} = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_l x_{ijl}$ and $i=1, 2, \dots, t, j=1, 2, \dots, b$ and $l=1, 2, \dots, n$

Under the null hypothesis, the statistic F follows the Snedecor's F with $(b-1)$ and $(tbn - b - t + 1)$ degrees of freedom, and for alternative, follows non-central F-distribution. After using the Gehan score (eq. 5) and Log-rank (eq. 6) on the F test, it is denoted as FU and FL, respectively.

2. Simulation Results

In this section, we summarized the empirical levels and power results of the study of the test statistic for the small sample approximation. Also, we want to know how block effects affect the tests' performance. Data were generated through simulation techniques from exponential distributions and Weibull distributions to assess the performance of the tests. In this section, we summarized the empirical levels and power results of the study of the test statistic. For comparing empirical levels and power results of the test statistic, 10000 iterations were simulated, and the appropriate chi-square distributions were configured for randomly right-censored observations. The proportions of hypothesis rejection at a 5 % significance level were listed for generated random numbers. Proportions of rejections in the null hypothesis to

the overall replications provide the empirical level of the test statistic to the H_0 and the power of the alternative hypothesis.

The combination of t , b and n i.e., no of treatments, blocks, and no of observations respectively are tabulated in Tables for designing the simulation process. The values of the block effects β_j are given in the table. The censoring distributions are uniformly distributed between 0 and M , where M is chosen to achieve a 25% expected censoring for exponential distributions. The value of $M = 3.9207$ is considered for exponential and uniform censoring distributions. Again, the value of $M = 3.6256$ is taken to get the expected 25% censoring for Weibull distributions to deal with the uniform censoring distributions. The empirical level and power outputs are summarized in the following tables below.

Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya suggested first calculating the critical values of the error distributions before computations of power values of the S_1^* statistic. The critical values of S_1^* under the null hypothesis for uniform censoring distributions are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1
Critical Values of the Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya (S_1^*) test

t	b	n	Uniform Censoring		t	b	n	Uniform Censoring	
			Exp. Dist.	Weibull dist.				Exp. Dist.	Weibull dist.
3	3	3	13.1688	13.1070	5	3	3	14.2173	14.1854
3	3	4	13.1495	13.1377	5	3	4	14.7650	14.7265
3	3	6	13.2272	13.3932	5	3	6	14.7456	14.8377
3	3	8	13.6235	13.5953	5	3	8	14.8915	14.8753
3	3	10	13.3693	13.3751	5	3	10	14.6135	14.5620
3	4	4	13.2703	13.3267	5	4	4	15.2247	15.1874
3	5	3	13.7128	13.7616	5	5	3	14.6479	14.6348
3	5	4	13.6316	13.4514	5	5	4	15.2247	15.1874
3	5	6	13.2254	13.2824	5	5	6	14.8804	14.9794
3	5	8	13.5205	13.4378	5	5	8	14.7577	14.7736
3	5	10	13.4874	13.4474	5	5	10	14.6732	14.6131
3	6	4	13.6582	13.6187	5	6	4	15.0721	15.0676
3	8	4	13.4281	20.7732	5	8	4	14.9970	27.7382
3	8	10	13.7928	32.8020	5	8	10	14.8352	47.1337
3	10	4	13.3725	43.8252	5	10	4	14.8920	66.9093
3	10	10	13.7306	91.9524	5	10	10	14.63	146.93

In their study, Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya discussed the treatments' main effects, only fixing their block effects using exponential censoring. They provided critical values and empirical powers of treatment effects of the statistic for some of the distributions. In our study, we have computed the empirical powers of all the statistics after changing and fixing both treatment and block effects using uniform censoring.

Table 2

Empirical Level and Power of Test Statistics under Exponential Distribution with Uniform Censoring for fixed t and b at level $\alpha = .05$.

t b n	Treatment Effects α_i	Block Effects β_j	S_1^*	TU	TL	FTU	FTL	FU	FL
3 3 3	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0468	.0387	.0400	.0438	.0435	.0505	.0345
3 3 4			.0528	.0480	.0516	.0476	.0464	.0502	.0342
3 3 6			.0510	.0446	.0524	.0455	.0451	.0461	.0338
3 3 8			.0480	.0488	.0507	.0463	.0465	.0503	.0324
3 3 10			.0516	.0494	.0517	.0526	.0498	.0493	.0502
3 3 3	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0394	.0402	.0423	.0461	.0412	.0439	.0438
3 3 4			.0427	.0461	.0466	.0468	.0426	.0459	.0457
3 3 6			.0464	.0438	.0494	.0458	.0419	.0420	.0421
3 3 8			.0482	.0503	.0507	.0482	.0457	.0488	.0487
3 3 10			.0452	.0481	.0537	.0517	.0498	.0481	.0480
3 3 3	1 2 1	0 0 0	.2666	.1510	.1630	.1417	.1409	.1592	.0978
3 3 4			.2941	.2049	.2170	.1968	.1951	.2113	.1116
3 3 6			.4371	.3639	.3640	.2171	.2961	.3026	.1328
3 3 8			.5135	.4070	.4161	.4058	.4047	.1417	.1484
3 3 10			.7837	.5550	.5515	.4532	.4096	.4345	.1616
3 3 3	1 3 5	0 0 2	.4955	.4396	.4903	.4513	.4509	.4866	.4214
3 3 4			.5939	.6268	.6469	.6267	.6264	.6346	.5044
3 3 6			.8971	.8215	.8178	.7163	.8261	.8242	.5407
3 3 8			.9995	.9316	.9513	.9277	.9275	.9337	.6309
3 3 10			.9999	.9920	.9850	.9654	.9515	.9550	.6726

Table 3

Empirical Level and Power of Test Statistics under Weibull Distribution with Uniform Censoring fixed t and b at level $\alpha = .05$

t b n	Treatment Effects α_i	Block Effects β_j	S_1^*	TU	TL	FTU	FTL	FU	FL
3 3 3	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0499	.0485	.0427	.0438	.0435	.0576	.0375
3 3 4			.0473	.0444	.0462	.0476	.0464	.0514	.0382
3 3 6			.0482	.0462	.0577	.0453	.0451	.0498	.0392
3 3 8			.0487	.0492	.0640	.0463	.0465	.0502	.0324
3 3 10			.0498	.0470	.0639	.0530	.0488	.0466	.0492

3 3 3	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0378	.0469	.0488	.0502	.0447	.0514	.0525
3 3 4			.0406	.0459	.0499	.0452	.0399	.0510	.0521
3 3 6			.0457	.0461	.0537	.0462	.0393	.0472	.0468
3 3 8			.0450	.0504	.0517	.0495	.0458	.0517	.0464
3 3 10			.0454	.0443	.0538	.0513	.0467	.0439	.0504
3 3 3	1 2 1	0 0 0	.2069	.1722	.1787	.1409	.1207	.1692	.1231
3 3 4			.3109	.2677	.2602	.1968	.1664	.2056	.1287
3 3 6			.3544	.2723	.2649	.2811	.2491	.2993	.1701
3 3 8			.4089	.3706	.3616	.3750	.3415	.3919	.2526
3 3 10			.5760	.4859	.4826	.3636	.3473	.3325	.3236
3 3 3	1 3 5	0 0 2	.4795	.4288	.4623	.4024	.3734	.4547	.4294
3 3 4			.7243	.5780	.6247	.5795	.5466	.5935	.5510
3 3 6			.8544	.7968	.8443	.8151	.7978	.7998	.7242
3 3 8			.9567	.9061	.9448	.9247	.9192	.9084	.8496
3 3 10			.9791	.9592	.9834	.9740	.9721	.9591	.9168

In table 2 and table 3 we estimate the empirical level and empirical power of three equal and unequal different treatment effects with fixed treatment and blocks for different number of observations using Exponential and Weibull distributions. Results depict that for both distributions in case of equal treatment effects, Woolson-Lachenbruch type method for log-rank method (TL) method is comparatively better than others but for unequal three treatment effects S_1^* gives a significant result than all of them.

Table 4
Empirical Level and Power of Test Statistics under Exponential Distribution with Uniform Censoring at level $\alpha = .05$

t b n	Treatment Effects(α_i)	Block Effects (β_j)	S_1^*	TU	TL	FTU	FTL	FU	FL
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0407	.0422	.0409	.0382	.0393	.0501	.0478
3 5 4			.0437	.0457	.0467	.0420	.0350	.0526	.0505
3 8 4			.0516	.0496	.0489	.0453	.0413	.0508	.0486
3 10 4			.0496	.0486	.0466	.0459	.0451	.0505	.0462
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 1	.0430	.0461	.0452	.0492	.0481	.0422	.0421
3 5 4			.0447	.0486	.0505	.0453	.0454	.0452	.0451
3 8 4			.0465	.0466	.0513	.0468	.0445	.0467	.0467
3 10 4			.0530	.0511	.0529	.0459	.0466	.0416	.0422
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0427	.0461	.0466	.0468	.0426	.0490	.0459
3 5 4			.0492	.0486	.0485	.0474	.0450	.0464	.0449
3 8 4			.0481	.0466	.0499	.0468	.0418	.0489	.0447
3 10 4			.0591	.0511	.0538	.0464	.0445	.0495	.0457
3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0516	.0494	.0676	.0526	.0498	.0493	.0502
3 5 10			.0485	.0501	.0621	.0521	.0482	.0504	.0499
3 8 10			.0503	.0511	.0622	.0470	.0463	.0497	.0497
3 10 10			.0509	.0480	.0624	.0468	.0474	.0467	.0436

3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 1	.0478	.0481	.0526	.0520	.0511	.0477	.0417
3 5 10			.0476	.0513	.0523	.0514	.0507	.0514	.0499
3 8 10			.0467	.0527	.0534	.0469	.0440	.0510	.0487
3 10 10			.0489	.0482	.0541	.0475	.0432	.0467	.0416
3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0452	.0481	.0508	.0517	.0498	.0482	.0481
3 5 10			.0468	.0513	.0516	.0519	.0512	.0503	.0503
3 8 10			.0483	.0512	.0528	.0466	.0454	.0507	.0457
3 10 10			.0464	.0482	.5230	.0459	.0470	.0473	.0449
3 3 10	.5 1 .7	0 0 0	.2933	.3621	.4693	.3999	.3755	.3610	.2649
3 5 10			.4982	.5802	.5688	.6201	.5017	.3790	.4346
3 8 10			.7399	.7911	.8248	.8380	.8164	.6393	.6273
3 10 10			.8768	.8810	.9166	.9127	.8940	.7785	.7423
3 3 10	.5 1 .7	0 0 2	.1970	.2158	.2459	.2502	.2290	.2148	.1778
3 5 10			.3839	.4402	.3939	.4822	.3679	.2633	.3435
3 8 10			.6902	.6962	.7087	.7553	.7235	.5373	.5529
3 10 10			.8507	.8206	.8556	.8669	.8379	.6926	.6807

Table 5

Empirical Level and Power of Test Statistics under Weibull Distribution with Uniform Censoring at level $\alpha = .05$

t b n	Treatment Effects α_i	Block Effects β_j	S_1^*	TU	TL	FTU	FTL	FU	FL
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0436	.0415	.0402	.0399	.0378	.0536	.0431
3 5 4			.0435	.0413	.0493	.0433	.0391	.0519	.0490
3 8 4			.0575	.0816	.0517	.0418	.0430	.0461	.0421
3 10 4			.0490	.0471	.0492	.0439	.0431	.0475	.0450
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 1	.0477	.0464	.0514	.0437	.0409	.0517	.0505
3 5 4			.0456	.0480	.0515	.0445	.0424	.0493	.0455
3 8 4			.0462	.0526	.0523	.0436	.0452	.0512	.0469
3 10 4			.0430	.0498	.0521	.0466	.0426	.0484	.0419
3 3 4	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0488	.0464	.0499	.0452	.0422	.0502	.0519
3 5 4			.0498	.0480	.0505	.0490	.0458	.0484	.0461
3 8 4			.0482	.0468	.0509	.0457	.0442	.0510	.0461
3 10 4			.0502	.0498	.0532	.0468	.0457	.0487	.0437
3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 0	.0498	.0470	.0528	.0516	.0488	.0466	.0500
3 5 10			.0494	.0514	.0526	.0518	.0499	.0514	.0513
3 8 10			.0513	.0503	.0518	.0473	.0451	.0493	.0492
3 10 10			.0510	.0498	.0516	.0468	.0476	.0487	.0475
3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 1	.0505	.0449	.0523	.0530	.0437	.0447	.0458
3 5 10			.0507	.0481	.0521	.0512	.0482	.0474	.0501
3 8 10			.0527	.0491	.0516	.0465	.0440	.0470	.0493
3 10 10			.0519	.0492	.0514	.0474	.0451	.0464	.0496
3 3 10	1 1 1	0 0 2	.0454	.0449	.0518	.0513	.0467	.0439	.0504
3 5 10			.0479	.0481	.0514	.0509	.0480	.0485	.0513
3 8 10			.0523	.0491	.0538	.0466	.0464	.0444	.0477
3 10 10			.0519	.0492	.0530	.0482	.0465	.0468	.0511
3 3 10	.5 1 .7	0 0 0	.5128	.4125	.4693	.4508	.4102	.4113	.1991

3 5 10			.6682	.6514	.5093	.6719	.5200	.4105	.3234
3 8 10			.8378	.8580	.8248	.8811	.8903	.7219	.4858
3 10 10			.9399	.9279	.9166	.9394	.9347	.8466	.5857
3 3 10	.5 1 .7	0 0 2	.3556	.2527	.2459	.2564	.2358	.2518	.1717
3 5 10			.5556	.5688	.3939	.5079	.3709	.2743	.2346
3 8 10			.7798	.7875	.7087	.8036	.8200	.6198	.4245
3 10 10			.9089	.8883	.8556	.8939	.8932	.7742	.5023

Table 4 and table 5 summarizes the empirical level and empirical powers of fixed three equal and unequal treatment effects with different block effects.

Table 6

Empirical powers of test statistics under Exponential Distribution with exponential censoring at $\alpha = .05$

t	b	n	Treatment Effects (α_i)	Block	S_1^*	TG	TL	FU	FL	FTU	FTL
5	3	4	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0	.0599	.0443	.0459	.0465	.0184	.0474	.0471
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0	.6302	.5984	.5710	.6064	.2007	.5996	.5981
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2	.4352	.4014	.3606	.4110	.1759	.3999	.3985
			1 2 3 1 1	0 2 4	.8056	.7834	.8635	.7900	.6221	.2015	.2005
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0	.6492	.6077	.6926	.6167	.5437	.7848	.7846
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 4	.4038	.3579	.4138	.3654	.3744	.3501	.3501
5	5	4	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0576	.0450	.0567	.0457	.0243	.0475	.0466
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.8928	.8629	.8728	.8619	.2227	.8715	.8707
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2 4 6	.4022	.3523	.3328	.3511	.1746	.3704	.3702
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9717	.9385	.9863	.9628	.8478	.9598	.9598
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 2 4 6	.6350	.5280	.6757	.5905	.5536	.6004	.6004
5	5	6	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0598	.0485	.0674	.0512	.0316	.0483	.0480
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.9842	.9771	.9858	.9776	.2406	.9754	.9752
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2 4 6	.5949	.5571	.5504	.5619	.2052	.5569	.5554
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9974	.9942	.9994	.9963	.9306	.9973	.9973
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 2 4 6	.8342	.7576	.8874	.8134	.6957	.8113	.8113
5	5	6	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0598	.0485	.0674	.0512	.0316	.0483	.0480
			1 1 1 1 1.5	0 0 0 0 0	.2444	.2193	.2446	.2251	.0584	.2190	.2173
			1 1.5 2 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.6677	.6295	.6124	.6341	.1464	.5670	.5677
			1 1.5 2 2.5 3	0 0 0 0 0	.9091	.8937	.9434	.8522	.5761	.8958	.8955
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9974	.9962	.9994	.9963	.9306	.9977	.9973
			1 1 1 1.5 2	0 0 0 0 0	.6619	.6309	.6602	.6361	.1439	.6281	.6258

Table 7

Empirical powers of test statistics under Weibull Distribution with exponential censoring at $\alpha = .05$

t	b	n	Treatment Effects (α_i)	Block	S_1^*	TG	TL	FU	FL	FTU	FTL
5	3	4	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0	.0599	.0447	.0500	.0469	.0177	.0474	.0471
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0	.6081	.5607	.6791	.5323	.5669	.5632	.5104
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2	.4142	.3655	.5887	.3837	.3231	.3589	.2899
			1 2 3 1 1	0 2 4	.2064	.1754	.4703	.1866	.1555	.1523	.1744
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0	.8060	.7598	.9353	.7868	.6541	.7643	.6020
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 4	.3147	.2614	.6721	.2904	.2395	.2169	.4451
5	5	4	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0576	.0499	.0534	.0492	.0253	.0475	.0466
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.8577	.8280	.9128	.8317	.8262	.8268	.7940
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2 4 6	.3617	.3229	.7615	.3291	.2463	.2636	.5550
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9736	.9541	.9986	.9616	.9269	.9590	.9108
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 2 4 6	.5529	.5020	.9395	.5237	.4159	.4089	.8753
5	5	6	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0528	.0472	.0654	.0480	.0332	.0483	.0480
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.9699	.9565	.9923	.9612	.9511	.9592	.9470
			1 2 3 1 1	0 0 2 4 6	.5351	.4778	.9655	.4941	.3623	.4417	.7593
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9982	.9976	.9978	.9986	.9943	.9978	.9950
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 2 4 6	.7675	.7197	.9988	.7472	.6233	.6533	.9656
5	5	6	1 1 1 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.0528	.0472	.0654	.0480	.0332	.0483	.0480
			1 1 1 1 1.5	0 0 0 0 0	.2495	.2170	.3290	.2250	.2044	.2264	.2182
			1 1.5 2 1 1	0 0 0 0 0	.5907	.5943	.7838	.6073	.5530	.6165	.5923
			1 1.5 2 2.5 3	0 0 0 0 0	.9097	.8880	.9953	.9028	.8080	.8941	.8522
			1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0 0 0	.9982	.9976	1.000	.9986	.9943	.9978	.9950
1 1 1 1.5 2	0 0 0 0 0	.6451	.6115	.7752	.6275	.5558	.6131	.5905			

Table 6 and table 7 included the empirical level and power values of five different treatment effects. Here, we also three and five different block sizes for both exponential and Weibull distribution.

3. Discussions

Table 2 and 3 contains the simulation results of three treatments and three blocks with increasing number of observations for exponential and Weibull distribution with uniform censoring respectively. Simulation results show that the Woolson-Lachenbruch type test for log-rank TL did well in equal treatment groups with different block effects. Whereas after changing the treatment effects and block effects the result indicates that Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya’s test based on U-statistics is significantly well performed compared to the Friedman type test and F-tests.

Table 4 and 5 represents the empirical results of three treatments with 4 and 10 number of observations for different monotonically increasing block effects shows that large number of observations TL performs well in equal treatment effects and for unequal FTU comparatively well in exponential distribution but S_1^* also well in case of some small observations. But in case of Weibull distribution S_1^* shows well for large observations in equal treatment effects than others and for unequal treatment effects a mixed results noticed for uniform censoring. Overall, the test TL indicates large power values compared to others.

Table 6 is about of five different treatments with three and five block effects for exponential distribution with uniform censoring shows a mixed result. Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya's test is slightly less than the Woolson-Lachenbruch log-rank TL test but better than the Gehan score type and other rank type methods. We noticed all the seventh test controls the nominal level. However, in Table 7, Weibull distribution with uniform censoring TL shows good performance almost all those selected treatment effects.

From the above tables, we can say that Woolson-Lachenbruch type log-rank TL statistic still performs well in both censoring for uniform and exponential distributions.

4. Conclusion

In this chapter, we aimed to check the performance of Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya's test to test the equality of main effects in two-way design based on U-statistics with right censored data and comparison with Gehan score and Log-rank related earlier tests. Shanubhogue and Raykundaliya's generalized version of the Gore test for main effects in randomized block design with uniform censoring in case of exponential and Weibull distribution generated datasets is comparatively better for equal small samples than Gehan score-related tests and log-rank-related tests except TL statistic.

Statements and Declarations

Funding: The authors are confirmed that this manuscript was prepared without any financial assistance or grant funding.

Conflict of Interest: Authors disclose no potential conflict of interest in this work.

5. Reference

1. Friedman, M. (1937). The use of ranks to avoid the assumption of normality implicit in the analysis of variance. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 32(200), 675-701.
2. Lehmann, E. L. (1964). Asymptotically nonparametric inference in some linear models with one observation per cell. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 726-734.
3. Bhapkar, V. P., & Gore, A. P. (1973). A distribution-free test for symmetry in hierarchical data. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 3(4), 483-489.
4. Gore, A. P. (1975). Some nonparametric tests and selection procedures for main effects in two-way layouts. *Annals of the Institute of Statistical Mathematics*, 27, 487-500.
5. Gehan, E. A. (1965). A generalized Wilcoxon test for comparing arbitrarily singly-censored samples. *Biometrika*, 52(1-2), 203-224.
6. Breslow, N. (1970). A generalized Kruskal-Wallis test for comparing K samples subject to unequal patterns of censorship. *Biometrika*, 57(3), 579-594.
7. Patel, K. M. (1975). A generalized Friedman test for randomized block designs when observations are subject to arbitrary right censorship. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 4(4), 389-395.
8. Shanubhogue, A., & Raykundaliya, D. P. (2014). A Test for Main Effects When Observations are Randomly Right Censored. *Advances and Applications in Statistics*, 39(1), 1.
9. Groggel, D. J., Schaefer, R. L., & Skillings, J. H. (1987). Procedures for analyzing block designs with censored data. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 16(2), 431-444.

10. Breslow, N. (1970). A generalized Kruskal-Wallis test for comparing K samples subject to unequal patterns of censorship. *Biometrika*, 57(3), 579-594.